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ALGORITHM FOR PREDICTING THE PROGRESSION OF ORAL DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH TUBULOINTERSTITIAL KIDNEY DISEASE

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ABSTRACT

Studies on the dental morbidity of people suffering from chronic kidney disease (CKD) have shown that they are more likely to have pathology of teeth, periodontal and oral mucosa than healthy individuals of the same age group. A particularly unfavorable state of dental health was noted in people suffering from chronic renal failure, regardless of their presence on hemodialysis therapy. It was revealed that individuals suffering from chronic pyelonephritis and chronic glomerulonephritis have differences in the condition of periodontal tissues, compared with practically healthy individuals of the same age group.

Keywords: Proinflammatory cytokines, tubulointerstitial kidney system.

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АЛГОРИТМ ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЯ ПРОГРЕССИРОВАНИЯ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ПОЛОСТИ РТА У БОЛЬНЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЕМ ТУБУЛОИНТЕРСТИЦИАЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ПОЧЕК

АННОТАЦИЯ

Исследования по изучению стоматологической заболеваемости людей, страдающих хронической болезнью почек (ТИБП) показали, что у них чаще встречается патология зубов, пародонта и слизистой оболочки полости рта, чем у здоровых лиц аналогичной возрастной группы. Особенно неблагоприятное состояние стоматологического здоровья отмечено у лиц, страдающих хронической почечной недостаточностью, не зависимо от их нахождения на гемодиализной терапии. Выявлено, что у лиц, страдающих хроническим пиелонефритом и хроническим гломерулонефритом имеются различий в состоянии тканей пародонта, по сравнению с практически здоровыми лицами этой же возрастной группы.

Ключивые слова: Провоспалительные цитокины, тубулоинтерстициальной системы почек.

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ОҒИЗ БЎШЛИҒИ КАСАЛЛИКЛАРИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШИНИ ПРОГНОЗ КИЛИШ АЛГОРИТМИ ТУБУЛОИНТЕРСТИЦИАЛ БУЙРАК ТИЗИМИ КАСАЛЛИГИ БЎЛГАН БЕМОРЛАРДА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Сурункали буйрак касаллиги билан оғриган одамларнинг тиш касалликларини ўрганиш бўйича тадқиқотлар шуни кўрсатдики, улар худди шундай ёш гуруҳидаги соғлом одамларга караганда тиш, периодонтал ва оғиз шиллиқ қаватининг патологиясини тез-тез учратишади. Сурункали буйрак етишмовчилигидан азият чекадиган одамларда, айниқса, гемодиализ терапиясида бўлишидан қатъи назар, тиш соғлиғининг ноқулай ҳолати қайд этилган. Сурункали пиелонефрит ва сурункали гломерулонефрит билан оғриган одамларда пародонт тўқималарнинг ҳолатида бир хил ёшдаги деярли соғлом шахслар билан таққослаганда фарқлар борлиги аниқланди.

Калит сўзлар: яллиғланишга қарши ситокинлар, буйрак тубулоинтерстициал тизими.

Introduction. In patients with TIBP, severe forms of chronic generalized periodontitis are significantly more often detected (CPI 3.43-3.52), they need to remove tartar deposits in 98%-100% with unsatisfactory individual oral hygiene (hygiene index 2.44-3.56), and diseases of the oral mucosa, lips and tongue are diagnosed in 16.3%-39.0% of cases. Therefore, the unsatisfactory hygienic condition of the oral cavity in persons suffering from chronic renal failure for a long time, as well as the often severe inflammatory pathology of periodontal disease, require the development of special recommendations for oral care and treatment of periodontal pathology in such patients.

The aim of the study was to identify markers of renal kidney damage to predict the progression of periodontal diseases.

Material and methods of research

Therefore, we have improved organizational and therapeutic and preventive measures aimed at improving the quality of dental health in people suffering from chronic renal failure. They have a complex of therapeutic and preventive measures for the rehabilitation of organs and tissues of the oral cavity, which was carried out at the place of their attachment, included the treatment of uncomplicated caries, pulpitis, periodontitis (surgical methods or conservative methods, taking into account indications and contraindications), treatment of inflammatory periodontal pathology, which consisted in conducting professional controlled oral hygiene with subsequent treatment gingivitis or periodontitis, whose treatment methods were chosen taking into account the severity of periodontal pathology.

At the same time, the study of dental health in patients of the control and main groups showed that carious cavities were diagnosed, respectively, in 198 and 222 teeth, non-carious lesions (mainly wedge-shaped defects) in 67 and 72 teeth, pulpitis and periodontitis were diagnosed in 34 and 10, 35 and 11 teeth, respectively. The hygienic condition of the oral cavity was unsatisfactory, both in the main (hygiene index 3.56 ± 0.12) and in the control group of patients (3.52 ± 0.13). The Schiller-Pisarev test was positive in all the examined main and control groups. The PMA index in the control group was 56.4%, in the main group - 61.1%, and the iodine number of Svrakov, respectively, was 2.83 ± 0.22 conl. units and 2.84 ± 0.24 conl. units. The value of the KPI index before the start of therapeutic and preventive measures was 3.54 ± 0.21 conl. units in the control group, in the main group groups - 3.52 ± 0.22 conl. units, which corresponded to the severe course of periodontal pathology. An analysis of the effectiveness of dental treatment and prophylactic measures in the control group of patients suffering from CRF showed that 28.28% and 43.28% of the fillings applied for caries and non-carious lesions became defective, respectively, a year later, and ineffective treatment of pulpitis

and periodontitis was noted, respectively, in 14.71% and 80.0% of clinical cases. In the control group, a year after the oral sanitation measures, the hygienic condition of the oral cavity improved somewhat ($p < 0.05$), but still remained unsatisfactory (hygiene index 2.07 ± 0.46 units). A positive Schiller-Pisarev test was determined in 27 (81.82%) patients from this group ($p < 0.05$), the PMA index was 32.3% ($p < 0.05$), the value of the Svrakov iodine number was 1.93 ± 0.21 units ($p < 0.05$), and the KPI index was 2.31 ± 0.18 ($p < 0.05$), which corresponded to the average severity of the course of periodontal pathology.

One of the main indicators of the immunity of the mucous membranes is the content of secretory immunoglobulins. It should be noted that the ratio of immunoglobulins in the oral cavity is different than in the blood serum. Secretory antibodies of the oral fluid are immunoglobulins of the IgA and IgM classes and are of local origin. They are produced by plasma cells located under the basement membrane in the connective tissue layer of the mucous membrane - in its own lamina (lamina propria) (M.J. Taba, J. Kinney et al., 2005). The main role of antibodies of the class

IgA consists in preventing the attachment of bacteria and microbial toxins to the epithelium, the absorption of harmful xenobiotics. sIgA are an important element of the first line of defense against pathogens. Saliva contains much more sIgA than other immunoglobulins: for example, in saliva secreted by the parotid glands, the ratio of IgA/IgG is 400 times higher than that in blood serum (C.A. Janeway, P. Travers, 1996). As can be seen from the data presented in Table 7, the level of sIgA in the control group did not differ after 1 year, whereas in the group of patients taking biocorrectors, the content of sIgA in saliva increased, significantly differing from the indicators of the control group ($p < 0.05$).

The data obtained by us coincide with the results of studies by other authors who noted the positive effect of biocorrectors on the content of immunoglobulin A (V.G. Bepalov, A.K. Iordanishvili et al., 2007; A.K. Iordanishvili, F.I. Komarov, 2007). As is known, the sIgA level reflects the status of local immunity aimed at the formation of protective mechanisms to changes in external conditions, adaptation to stress. An increase in the level of sIgA leads to a decrease in the probability of the appearance of pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microflora and the displacement of protective groups of microflora in the oral cavity and, thus, leads to a decrease in the activity of inflammatory processes (N. Malathi, S. Mythili, H. Vasanthi, 2014).

As with any infectious and inflammatory diseases, the pathogenesis of CKD is based on the launch of cytokine cascade reactions, which includes the production of both pro- (IL-1P, TNF α , IL-6) and anti-inflammatory cytokines (IL-10, RAIL, TGFP). Thus, it was found that in chronic pyelonephritis, interleukins are synthesized in response to inflammation by uroepithelial cells of the proximal part of the tubular part of the nephron. Changes in the cytokine profile of saliva in various diseases can be considered an important diagnostic indicator that reveals the development of inflammation. The predominance of pro- or anti-inflammatory cytokines leads to a decrease in the effectiveness of inflammation, the development of purulent complications or autoimmune pathology.

A significant decrease in the concentration of IL-6 and IL-8 was found in comparison with the control. A drop in the level of IL-8, the main chemotactic factor of neutrophils, on the one hand reduces the level of local immunity, but on the other hand inhibits the production of oxygen radicals by neutrophils that damage the oral mucosa, contributing to the activation of repair processes.

Proinflammatory cytokines ensure the attraction of effector cells (neutrophils, macrophages) to the focus of inflammation, stimulate bactericidal, phagocytic activity, and start the launch of the antigen-specific immune response of the latter. Excessive and generalized production of proinflammatory cytokines leads to the development of dysfunctions in organs. To avoid an excessive inflammatory response, negative control mechanisms are triggered in the body, stimulating the appearance of soluble inhibitors of pro-inflammatory cytokines and the production of anti-inflammatory cytokines. For example, the production of the IL-1p receptor antagonist has a permanent character, limiting (competitively) activation of cells under the influence of IL-1p and simultaneously exhibiting inflammatory activity (S.A. Ketlinsky, 2008).

There was no significant difference between both groups in the content of the IL-1 receptor antagonist (RAIL) in saliva, as well as IL-4 and the main anti-inflammatory cytokine - IL-10.

The conducted clinical study also showed that for effective dental rehabilitation of patients suffering from chronic renal insufficiency, their dynamic observation and treatment by a dentist is necessary. At the same time, the developed algorithm for professional oral hygiene twice a year, against the background of general and local therapy used in the main group, allows achieving good long-term results in the treatment of caries, non-carious lesions of the teeth, as well as diseases of the oral mucosa. Treatment of pulpitis and periodontitis were often not effective, both in the control and the main group of patients suffering from chronic renal failure, which is associated with reduced immunological reactivity and resistance of the body of such patients against the background of chronic kidney disease therapy. Obviously, it is necessary to develop a complex of therapeutic and preventive measures aimed at improving the effectiveness of treatment of complicated forms of caries in such patients, taking into account their comorbid pathology.

Prospects for further development of the topic lie in the study of ways to improve the treatment of complicated dental caries (pulpitis, periodontitis) in patients suffering from chronic kidney disease, as well as in improving their dental care, including dental prosthetics, carried out taking into account comorbid pathology and aimed at improving the effectiveness of dental rehabilitation.

Diagnosis of prognostication of variants of the course of tubulo-interstitial kidney disease in patients with chronic generalized periodontitis is one of the urgent tasks of dentistry and nephrology. The reason for this is the growth of latent forms of this pathology, which greatly complicates their timely diagnosis, and therefore the search for additional criteria and informative signs of predicting the progression of TIBP in patients with a disease of the dental system is of particular importance. To solve this problem, we conducted a comparative assessment of the informativeness of anamnestic and clinical-paraclinical indicators of blood, oral fluid and urine. Considering that the accuracy of forecasting depends on the degree of informativeness of the parameters used and the integral assessment of the entire set of anamnestic and clinical laboratory data. The development of the prognostic algorithm included the following stages: preliminary selection of anamnestic and clinical-paraclinical criteria, according to which patients with favorable and progressive course of TIBP in patients with periodontal disease were significantly different. Thus, the developed comprehensive approach to predicting the progressive course of TIBP on the basis of clinical and pathogenetic indicators with an assessment of the level of functional parameters and cytokine status makes it possible to optimize the diagnosis and prediction of the course of various variants of this pathology in patients with TIBP combined chronic generalized periodontitis. The effectiveness of the proposed method for predicting the progression of TIBP in patients with combined pathology of the dental system reaches 82%, since the share of questionable results is 18%.

Research results and their discussion

Over the past 15-20 years, methods of diagnosis and dental rehabilitation of adults suffering from various diseases of the organs and tissues of the oral cavity have improved. This is due to the introduction of innovative technologies, new equipment, tools and materials into practical dentistry. At the same time, difficulties remain in the treatment of diseases of the teeth, periodontal and oral mucosa during dental rehabilitation of patients suffering from chronic kidney disease.

The main purpose of our study was to study the frequency of occurrence, features of the clinical course and to evaluate the effectiveness of treatment of major dental diseases in adults with chronic kidney disease. To achieve this goal, we solved the following tasks. The frequency and intensity of the course of caries and non-carious lesions of the hard tissues of the teeth in persons suffering from chronic kidney disease, the level of individual oral hygiene was studied, and the features of the clinical course of periodontal pathology and oral mucosa in various forms of chronic kidney disease were studied. In addition, a comparative assessment of the morphological structure and chemical composition of dental hard tissues was carried out in persons suffering from various forms of chronic kidney disease, including taking into account remineralizing therapy. Special attention in the study is paid to the clinical and functional characteristics of periodontal tissues and

oral mucosa in people suffering from chronic kidney disease using modern objective examination methods. The study concluded with an assessment of the effectiveness and improvement of the treatment of major dental diseases in people suffering from chronic kidney disease.

Conclusions

The progression of tubulo-interstitial kidney damage in patients with periodontal disease is characterized by an increase in urinary excretion of proinflammatory cytokines: IL-1, IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α , with a simultaneous decrease in urinary excretion of anti-inflammatory IL-10. At the same time, increased levels of IL-6 in the blood provide activation of humoral immunity, limiting the significance of cell-mediated immune reactions.

References.

1. Sh.R.Usmanova, A.A.Khadzhimetov, H.P.Komilov Assessment of local and humoral immunity in patients with chronic pyelonephritis // Dentistry science and practice, development prospects. Volgograd 2021 - p.221-222
2. Borisova O.V., Makovetskaya G.A., Terekhin S.S., Mazur L.I., Barinov I.V. Early detection of progression of chronic kidney disease: standard and modified diagnostic methods / Borisova O.V., Makovetskaya G.A., Terekhin S.S., Mazur L.I., Barinov I.V. // Pediatrics named after G.N. Sперansky. - 2012. - Vol. 91. - No. 6. - pp. 50-54.
3. Sh.R.Usmanova endotheliocyte dysfunction in patients with chronic generalized periodontitis/ Internauka. Moscow. 02,12,2020, pp.62-65
4. Borisova, O.V. Early detection of progression of chronic kidney disease: standard and modified diagnostic methods / O.V.Borisova, S.S. Terekhin, G.A. Makovetskaya, L.I. Mazur, I.V. Barinov // Pediatrics. 2012. Vol. 91. No. 6. pp. 50-54.
5. Velkov, V.V. Cystatin S: new opportunities and new tasks for laboratory diagnostics. Part 2 // Clinical and laboratory consultation. 2011. No. 1. pp. 27-38.
6. Craig, R.G. Periodontitis and the end-stage renal disease patient receiving hemodialysis maintenance therapy / R.G. Craig, P. Kotanko // Compend. Contin. Educ. Dent. - 2009 - № 30(8) - P. 544-549.
7. Fang, F. The clinical response and systemic effects of non-surgical periodontal therapy in end-stage renal disease patients: a 6-month randomized controlled clinical trial. / F. Fang, B. Wu, Q. Qu [et. al] // J. Clin. Periodontol. - 2015. - № 42 (6). - P. 537 - 546.
8. Ioannidou, E. Periodontitis Predicts Elevated C-reactive Protein Levels in Chronic Kidney Disease / E. Ioannidou, H. Swede, A. Dongari-Bagtzoglou // J. Dent. Res. - 2011. - № 90 (12). - P. 1411 - 1415.
9. Ioannidou, E. Tooth loss strongly associates with malnutrition in chronic kidney disease. / E. Ioannidou, H. Swede, G. Fares, J. Himmelfarb // J. Periodontol. - 2014. - № 85 (7). - P. 899 - 907.
10. Jain, S. Underlying kidney disease and duration of hemodialysis: an assessment of its effect on oral health / S. Jain, A. Singla, P. Basavaraj, S. Singh, K. Singh, H. Kundy // J. Clin. Diagn. Res. - 2014. - № 8 (5). - P.65 - 69.
11. Limeres, J. Early tooth loss in end-stage renal disease patients on haemodialysis. / J. Limeres, J.F. Garcez, J.S. [et al.] // Oral. Dis. - 2016. - № 68 (10). - P. 1125 - 1130.

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